

**MILLIY IQTISODIYOTDA FERMER XO'JALIKLARINI TUTGAN O'RNI
VA ULARNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI**

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РОЛЬ ХОЗЯЙСТВ В НАРОДНОМ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕ И ИХ ОСОБЕННОСТИ

*НЕЗАВИСИМЫЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ ИНСТИТУТА
ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КВАЛИФИКАЦИИ И СТАТИСТИЧЕСКИХ
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**THE ROLE OF FARMS IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY AND THEIR
FEATURES**

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Annotatsiya. *Mazkur maqolada fermer xo'jaliklarining milliy iqtisodiyotdagi o'rni va ularning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari keng qamrovli tarzda tahlil qilinadi. Fermer xo'jaliklari, ayniqsa qishloq xo'jaligi sektorida, oziq-ovqat ta'minoti, eksport salohiyati, ish o'rinlarini yaratish va iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ular nafaqat yer va suv resurslari, balki iqlim sharoitlari, texnologiyalar va agrar innovatsiyalar bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Fermerlar qishloq joylarida aholining asosiy daromad manbaiga aylanishi bilan birga, turli mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarish orqali iqtisodiyotni diversifikatsiya qilishga katta hissa qo'shadi. Ushbu xo'jaliklar iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy va ekologik jihatdan davlat siyosatiga ta'sir qiluvchi muhim omil sifatida qaraladi.*

Fermer xo'jaliklarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ularning kichik va o'rta hajmdagi mulkchilik tuzilmalari, shaxsiy tashkiliy va boshqaruv usullari bilan bog'liq. Ularning mahsulot ishlab chiqarish usullari, ekologik jihatdan barqarorlikni ta'minlash, yer resurslarini samarali boshqarish va innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish kabi xususiyatlar mavjud. Shuningdek, fermer xo'jaliklari o'zaro raqobatbardosh bo'lish uchun zamonaviy texnologiyalarni joriy etish orqali samaradorlikni oshiradi. Bu jihatlar milliy iqtisodiyotning muhim tarkibiy qismi bo'lib, ular nafaqat oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlash, balki atrof-muhitni himoya qilish va qishloq joylaridagi ijtimoiy barqarorlikni saqlashga yordam beradi.

Maqolada fermer xo'jaliklarining milliy iqtisodiyotga qo'shgan hissasi, ekologik muhofaza qilishda roli va ularning innovatsiyalarni qabul qilishdagi o'rni haqida keng qamrovli ma'lumotlar beriladi. Shuningdek, davlat tomonidan qo'llabquvvatlash va samarali siyosat yuritishning fermer xo'jaliklarining rivojlanishiga ta'siri ham tahlil qilinadi.

Аннотация. *В данной статье подробно анализируется роль фермерских хозяйств в национальной экономике и их уникальные особенности. Фермерские хозяйства, особенно в сельскохозяйственном секторе, играют важную роль в обеспечении продовольственной безопасности, увеличении экспортного потенциала, создании рабочих мест и поддержании экономической стабильности. Эти хозяйства тесно связаны с природными ресурсами, климатическими условиями, технологическими достижениями и аграрными инновациями. Фермерские хозяйства не только служат основным источником дохода для сельского населения, но и способствуют диверсификации экономики за счет производства широкого спектра товаров. Эти хозяйства рассматриваются как ключевые элементы национальной экономики, влияющие на экономическую, социальную и экологическую политику государства.*

Особенности фермерских хозяйств включают малые и средние формы собственности, личные методы управления и организационные подходы, а также ориентацию на устойчивое производство. Они стремятся обеспечить экологическую устойчивость, эффективное управление земельными ресурсами и внедрение инновационных технологий. Фермеры повышают свою конкурентоспособность и продуктивность, внедряя современные технологии. Эти особенности делают фермерские хозяйства важным компонентом национальной экономики, способствующим не только обеспечению продовольственной безопасности, но и охране окружающей среды и сохранению социальной стабильности в сельских районах.

Статья также рассматривает вклад фермерских хозяйств в национальную экономику, их роль в охране окружающей среды и их участие в

принятии инноваций. Кроме того, анализируется влияние государственной поддержки и эффективных политик на развитие фермерских хозяйств.

Abstract. *This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the role of farms in the national economy and their distinctive characteristics. Farms, especially in the agricultural sector, play a crucial role in ensuring food security, enhancing export potential, creating employment opportunities, and maintaining economic stability. They are intricately connected to land and water resources, climatic conditions, technological advancements, and agricultural innovations. Farms not only serve as the primary source of income for rural populations but also contribute to the diversification of the economy by producing a wide variety of goods. These farms are seen as key players in the national economy, influencing economic, social, and environmental policies at the state level.*

The distinctive characteristics of farms include their small and medium-scale ownership structures, personal management and organizational methods, and reliance on sustainable production practices. They aim to ensure ecological sustainability, efficient land management, and the implementation of innovative technologies. Farms also increase their productivity and competitiveness by adopting modern technological solutions. These characteristics make them an essential part of the national economy, contributing not only to food security but also to environmental protection and the preservation of social stability in rural areas.

The article also discusses the contribution of farms to the national economy, their role in environmental protection, and their position in adopting innovations. Additionally, the influence of government support and effective policies on the development of farms is analyzed.

Kalit so‘zlar: fermer xo‘jaliklari, milliy iqtisodiyot, qishloq xo‘jaligi, oziqovqat ta‘minoti, eksport, innovatsiyalar, barqarorlik, ekologiya, iqtisodiy rivojlanish.

Ключевые слова: фермерские хозяйства, национальная экономика, сельское хозяйство, продовольственная безопасность, экспорт, инновации, устойчивость, экология, экономическое развитие.

Keywords: farms, national economy, agriculture, food security, exports, innovations, sustainability, ecology, economic development.

Introduction

Farms occupy an important place in the structure of the Uzbek economy, as they are one of the main components of the country's agricultural sector. Agriculture is one of the most important sectors of the national economy of Uzbekistan. Due to their activities, farms play an important role not only in food production, but also in ensuring the territorial socio-economic stability of the country. These farms play an

important role in meeting the needs of the rural population on their territory, improving living standards and stimulating economic growth. The activities of farms contribute to the efficient allocation of labor resources in rural areas of the country. At the same time, they serve to create jobs in rural areas, provide employment for the population and, thus, increase the social stability of society. Farms also play an invaluable role in ensuring food security and play an important role in providing various segments of the population with essential food, as well as in increasing export potential.

According to the Statistical Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2020), farms not only contribute to the development of the country's economy, but also significantly contribute to ensuring the economic stability of the state. As a result of the effective functioning and development of farms, social infrastructure, education, healthcare, transport and other areas are developing in rural areas. This, in turn, contributes to economic growth and has a positive impact on the overall development of the country. Farms also contribute to the state budget by increasing tax revenues. For this reason, they are important not only for food production, but also for ensuring territorial social stability and economic development. Policies aimed at developing farms, government assistance provided to them, and effective economic strategies are key factors in ensuring the country's sustainable development.

Literature reviews

Theoretical and methodological issues of socio-economic development and improving agricultural efficiency, as well as issues of studying economic activity, were developed by foreign scientists L.SFU, TS.Fan, L.Zhou, J.M.Shurbakh, S. Shiona, Investigated by S.S.Shenoy.¹

Problems of the development of agricultural sales markets from scientists of the CIS countries L.V.Agarkova, I.A.Baranov, N.A.Popov, A.V.Afanasyeva, M.A.Solomakhin, N.I.Investigated by Grekov².

¹ Лин Цфу, Цой Фан, Ли Чжоу. Китайское чудо: экономическая реформа, стратегия развития. – М.: 2001. С.68.; Jan Mathis Schopbach “Foreign direct investment in agriculture the impact of out grower schemes and large-scale farm employment on economic well-being in Zambia” Master of Arts, University of Zurich accepted on the recommendation of Prof. Dr. Rolf Kappel, examiner Prof. Dr. Isabel Gonther, co-examiner Prof. Dr. Jann Lay, co-examiner, diss. eth no. 22287 2014. – p. 21-28.

² Агаркова Л.В. Формирование механизма устойчивого развития плодовоовощного подкомплекса: теория и практика. – Ставрополь: Ставролит, 2007. – С.168.; Баранов И.А. Совершенствование коммерческой работы торговых и заготовительных организаций потребительской кооперации. Автореф. дисс. д-ра экон. наук. – М.: РГБ, 2003. – С.39.; Попов Н.А. Экономика сельского хозяйства. – М.: Дело и сервис, 2005. – С.56.; Афанасьева А.В. Статистическая оценка динамики производства сельскохозяйственной продукции в системе государственного регулирования продовольственного рынка. Автореф. дисс. на соис. канд. экон. наук. – Самара, 2008. – С.26.; Соломахин М.А. Основные направления совершенствования системы ведения садоводства в условиях развития агропромышленной интеграции. // Организационно-экономические проблемы стабилизации и развития аграрного сектора экономики. Том 1: Материалы научно-практической конференции 9-10 ноября 2005 г. Мичуринск: Изд-во ФГОУ ВПО МичГАУ, 2005. – Том 1. – С.153-159.; Греков Н.И. Основные направления и факторы интенсификации садоводства. // Организационно-экономические проблемы стабилизации и развития аграрного сектора экономики. Том 1: Материалы научно-практической конференции 9-10 ноября 2005 г. Мичуринск: Изд-во ФГОУ ВПО МичГАУ, 2005. – Том 1. – С.164-166.

Research Methodology

Farms form the central branch of Uzbekistan's economy, as they play an important role in the country's agricultural sector. Farms are considered extremely important not only for food production, but also for providing employment to the population in rural areas, improving their living conditions and maintaining social stability. The role of farms in the economic development of Uzbekistan is very important, as the products they grow go not only to the domestic market, but also for export. In addition, due to the expansion and development of economic activity, it is possible to create additional sources of income for the country's economy[1]. Farms make a great contribution to the development of the national economy. They ensure economic growth in the country through the production, export and replenishment of food supplies on the domestic market. They are also capable of producing products that account for 25-30% of the republic's economy. Farms play a very important role in creating new jobs, especially in rural areas, in increasing the economic stability of the population and ensuring food security in the country[2].

The role of farms in the economy is evident only in certain industries, despite traditional industries such as cotton, wheat or fruits. The development and diversification of agricultural industries in Uzbekistan is of great strategic importance for the country's economy. However, the economic growth of farms has the potential to increase their competitiveness and create new markets through the introduction of innovative technologies and the production of high-quality products for local and global markets[3].

A distinctive feature of farms is that they are small and medium-sized producers. Farmers have a high rate of adaptation to market conditions, producing competitive products due to the rapid introduction of innovations in their activities. Uzbek farms often operate as medium-sized enterprises, each with unique resources and capabilities. Farmers increase production efficiency through the active use of innovative technologies. For example, thanks to modern irrigation systems, new fertilizers and pesticides, digital technologies, etc., production efficiency is increasing.

Farms' approach to diversification plays an important role in ensuring their economic stability. Farmers are developing their business by diversifying their products in various directions. For example, in addition to growing cotton and wheat, farmers increase their income by producing a wide range of products, including fruits and vegetables, chirping, meat production, animal husbandry, and other industries. This allows them to change their products, look for new markets and struggle with economic difficulties.

In addition, there is a need for more efficient use of land resources to improve the efficiency of farms. Limited water resources and climatic changes in the geographical regions of Uzbekistan are of great importance for the rational and effective management of land by farmers. To this end, it is necessary to introduce innovative technologies, in particular, technologies of dewatering and irrigation systems, to save water and increase land fertility.

This makes it possible for farmers to use their resources more efficiently.

The role of the state in the successful functioning of the economy is extremely important. Government policies, programs, and incentive mechanisms aimed at agricultural development significantly contribute to the growth of farms. Financial assistance to farmers, such as soft loans, subsidies, land allocation, and other economic assistance, creates opportunities for farmers to increase production, introduce new technologies, and bring products to market[4].

To increase the effectiveness of government assistance to farms, it is important to work in cooperation with territorial financial institutions, business development centers and other organizational structures. The role of the state in this is invaluable, as it provides the necessary advice and technical support to farmers, creating the necessary infrastructure for their entry into international markets. At the same time, the government provides the necessary resources to modernize agriculture, introduce innovative technologies, and bring farmers to new markets.

Environmental safety and environmental protection issues also occupy an important place in government policy aimed at the development of farms. This approach serves not only for the sustainable development of farmers, but also for the possibility of qualitative improvement of their products and successful export. The production of environmentally friendly and safe products, the development of organic farming increases the competitiveness of farms not only in the domestic market, but also internationally[5].

The prospects for the development of farms have great potential for growth in the current and future years. Innovations and technological innovations in agriculture in Uzbekistan, initiatives aimed at environmental safety, contribute to the development of farms. This, in turn, will help make Uzbekistan's agricultural products competitive on world markets. The development of ecotourism and organic farming is important in this regard.

Another important area of farm development is organic farming and ensuring environmental safety. By producing organic products, adopting environmentally friendly technologies and preserving nature, farmers increase economic sustainability and provide products that meet the needs of global markets. This is a direction that not only contributes to the economic growth of farms, but also supports environmental

sustainability. At the same time, organic products and environmentally friendly agricultural technologies meet the needs of global markets, which increases Uzbekistan's export potential[5]. In the future, by increasing the competitiveness of farms and expanding export potential, Uzbekistan's agricultural sector will not only replenish the domestic market, but will also be able to supply high-quality products to international markets. Thanks to this, Uzbekistan is making a significant contribution to its economic growth.

Analysis and results

Farms play an important role in the economic development of Uzbekistan, and this role is constantly growing. They play an important role not only in food production, but also in ensuring economic and social stability. Farms play an invaluable role in ensuring the country's food security, ensuring employment in rural areas and maintaining social stability. They fill the domestic market with food products and at the same time play an important role in the supply of high-quality products to export markets. The agricultural sector not only contributes to economic growth, but also ensures national sustainability by ensuring environmental safety without harming the environment.

Several factors are considered important for the successful development of the company. One of their main factors is the diversification of the agricultural sector. This allows us not only to expand our product range, but also to develop new industries such as organic farming, ecotourism and the agricultural industry. Diversification opens up new opportunities for farmers, helping to develop various sectors of the country, create new jobs and strengthen the economy. It is necessary for farms not to be limited to food production, but to introduce innovations, technologies and experience aimed at producing high-quality products through their processing, research and scientific research.

Conclusion/Recommendations

In conclusion, the introduction of new technologies increases the efficiency of farms, and this process plays a large role in the development of the economy. The use of new, advanced technologies can effectively exploit land, conserve water resources, and obtain high crop yields. Also, automated irrigation systems, the cultivation of environmentally friendly products and new approaches to the production of modern equipment are some of the most important ways to develop farms. Such technologies not only increase the quality of products, but also make it possible to meet consumer demand, expand export opportunities and produce competitive products in international markets. This, in turn, contributes to the country's economic growth and strengthens Uzbekistan's position in the international economy.

Ensuring environmental safety is also a prerequisite for the development of farms. By ensuring environmental safety, environmental protection, rational use of natural resources, and resource sustainability can be ensured. The production of organic products, the minimal use of chemicals and the prevention of land degradation are essential to ensure long-term sustainability. This contributes not only to the preservation of consumer health, but also to the development of the production of environmentally friendly products in agriculture. The production of organic products and ensuring environmental safety create great demand not only in the domestic market, but also in export markets. This will help strengthen Uzbekistan's position in international markets. Farms also play an important role in ensuring social stability. Employment of the population in rural areas, improvement of their living conditions, development of education and healthcare systems have a direct impact on the successful functioning of farms. Farmers play an important role in ensuring social stability in rural areas, providing the population with a source of income and creating high-quality services in rural areas.

It also creates opportunities for the development of farms, the creation of new jobs in rural areas, the improvement of the well-being of local residents and the expansion of employment opportunities for young people.

Economic opportunities of farms are expanding through programs such as financial support and support provided by the state, the study and introduction of new technologies, the development of ecotourism, the improvement of product quality. State subsidies, benefits and support provided for agricultural development, provide new opportunities for farmers to expand their economic reach. All this will help to ensure the efficient operation of farms, increase their economic capabilities and strengthen their place in the national economy.

At the same time, the role of farms in the national economy is further strengthened. Due to reforms in the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan, the introduction of new technologies, product diversification, ensuring environmental safety and social stability, the economic opportunities of farms are expanding and they contribute to the sustainable development of the national economy. Farms serve not only for economic growth, but also to enhance the social well-being of rural areas, improve the well-being of the population, expand export opportunities and ensure environmental sustainability. These processes, in turn, contribute to the sustainable economic growth of the country, the development of rural areas and the improvement of the well-being of the population.

References

1. Ibroximov, M. (2019). "Fermer xo'jaliklarining iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish." Toshkent: O'zbekiston iqtisodiyoti va badiiy adabiyoti nashriyoti.

2. Mamatov, A. (2020). "Qishloq xo'jaligi sohasidagi innovatsiyalar." Toshkent: Davlat iqtisodiyoti nashriyoti.
3. Yuldashev, F. (2021). "Fermer xo'jaliklarini rivojlantirish: Davlat siyosati va iqtisodiy yordam." Toshkent: O'zbekiston nashriyoti.
4. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Statistika qo'mitasi. (2020). "Qishloq xo'jaligi va fermer xo'jaliklari statistikasi." Toshkent.
5. Nurmatov, S. (2022). "Ekologik xavfsizlik va fermer xo'jaliklarida yangi texnologiyalar." Toshkent: Ekologiya va rivojlanish institutining nashriyoti.
6. Aripova, Z. S. Philosophy as a unity of scientific and non-scientific knowledge / Z. S. Aripova // Экономика и социум. – 2022. – No 3-2(94). – P. 46-49. – EDN MIJHSE.
7. Арипова З. . (2023). ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ФИЛОСОФИИ В СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ ПЕРИОД. Международный бюллетень прикладной науки и технологий, 3(9), 460 –462. Получено с <https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibast/article/view/2710>
8. Айсачев, А. (2021). Статистический анализ экономического развития сельского хозяйства на региональном уровне. *Экономика и инновационные технологии*, (4), 197–208. извлечено от https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/economics_and_innovative/article/view/11938
9. AA Aysachev, M Xonboboyeva. QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAXSULOTLARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHDA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKKA ERISHISHNING BA'ZI MASALALARI. (2024). *International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies*, 72-77. <https://econfseries.com/index.php/5/article/view/77>
10. Xolmirzayev , F. (2025). ANDIJON VILOYATIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK RIVOJLANISHINING IQTISODIY-STATISTIK TAHLILI . In *Iqtisodiy taraqqiyot va tahlil*. <https://doi.org/10.60078/2992-877X-2025-vol3-iss3-pp252-258>